

Knowledge and Attitude of Physiotherapy Students Towards Fitness

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Abstract: **Background:** Fitness is defined as the quality or state of being fit and healthy. The modern definition of fitness describes either a person or machine's ability to perform a specific function or a holistic definition of human adaptability to cope with various situations. This has led to an interrelation of human fitness and physical attractiveness that has mobilized global fitness and fitness equipment industries. Regarding specific function, fitness is attributed to persons who possess significant aerobic or anaerobic ability. A well-rounded fitness program improves a person in all aspects of fitness compared to practicing only one, such as only cardio/respiratory or only weight training. A comprehensive fitness program tailored to an individual typically focuses on one or more specific skills, [7] and on age [8] or health-related needs such as bone health [9]. Many sources [10] also cite mental, social and emotional health as an important part of overall fitness. This is often presented in textbooks as a triangle made up of three points, which represent physical, emotional, and mental fitness. Physical fitness has been shown to have benefits in preventing ill health and assisting recovery from injury or illness. Along with the physical health benefits of fitness, it has also been shown to have a positive impact on mental health as well by assisting in treating anxiety and depression [11]. Physical fitness can also prevent or treat many other chronic health conditions brought on by unhealthy lifestyle or aging as well and has been listed frequently as one of the most popular and advantageous self-care therapies [12]. Working out can also help some people sleep better by building up sleeping pressure and possibly alleviate some mood disorders in certain individuals. Physiotherapy students who are physically fit have higher chances of doing well in their professions which requires physical activity and adequate level of physical fitness. **Objective:** The primary aim of this study is to determine the knowledge and attitude towards fitness among physiotherapy students. **Methodology:** The study was conducted in Dr. BR. Ambedkar college of physiotherapy where questionnaire was framed on the basis of international physical activity questionnaire which was distributed among students to know about their attitude towards fitness. **Results:** There was a significant data which shows the students spend time for physical activity but not in a vigorous activity. **Conclusion:** The present study concluded that the students spends not much times for a fitness. The average time is 15 minutes a day.

Keywords: fitness, wellness, knowledge, health, exercise.

1. Introduction

Physical fitness is a condition of health and well-being and, more specifically, it refers to one's capacity for participating in certain sports, jobs, and daily activities. In general, good

nutrition is necessary to achieve physical fitness. A formal rehabilitation plan, enough rest, and moderately strenuous exercise are all recommended [1], [3].

Fitness was once understood to be the ability to complete the day's tasks without experiencing excessive exhaustion or sluggishness. Physical fitness is increasingly viewed as a gauge of the body's capacity to operate well in work and leisure activities, to be healthy, to resist hypokinetic disorders, to strengthen the immune system, and to respond to emergency situations. This is due to automation and changes in lifestyles [4].

A thorough fitness regimen designed for an individual often emphasizes one or more particular skills as well as age [8] or health-related requirements like bone health [9]. In addition to physical fitness, many sources emphasize the importance of mental, social, and emotional wellness. This is frequently depicted in textbooks as a triangle with three points that stand for physical, emotional, and mental wellness. It has been demonstrated that maintaining a healthy weight can help prevent disease and speed up the healing process after an injury or illness. In addition to its favourable effects on physical health, fitness has also been demonstrated to boost mental health by helping to cure sadness and anxiety. Additional chronic health issues that might be prevented or treated with exercise include [10], [11].

Recent studies have shown that skeletal muscle's function as an endocrine organ mediates many of the advantages of exercise. To put it another way, when muscles contract, a number of chemicals called myokines are released. These myokines have new tissue and tissue repair.

The physiotherapy professions required to engage in activities which demands good amount of strength, endurance, and flexibility. A reasonably high level of physical fitness is required to carry the job activities of a physiotherapist, as a student of physiotherapy, it is all more relevant that they understand the demand of the profession and their actual physical fitness.

The physiotherapist serves as role model for practicing healthy lifestyle behaviors, therefore the need to have good level of physical fitness to meet their job demands. It is important for physiotherapy students to understand the demands of the profession which they required in their future

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employment settings.

2. Review of Literature

A Awotidebe, JS Phillips: Knowledge and attitudes of physiotherapy students towards obesity. This study was based on the need to determine the knowledge and attitudes towards obese people among physiotherapy students, as they are well suited to address the intricacies of obesity and its related conditions. The study sample demonstrated average levels of knowledge regarding obesity with scores ranging from 3 to 9 on a scale of 10 with a mean score of 6.05. An overwhelming majority of the participants (> 80%) viewed obesity as largely a behavioural problem while nearly all the participants (97.6%) characterized obese people as lazy, unattractive, insecure and with lower self-esteem. This study has reinforced the need for a more focused approach to the education of physiotherapy students around obesity and obesity-related conditions, as well as the management thereof.

Merkiel S, Ratajczak: Food behaviour attitude towards nutritional knowledge in female fitness instructors and female fitness participants. The objective of this study was to compare food behaviour and attitude towards nutritional knowledge in fitness instructors and fitness participants. Statistically significant differences were observed in the studied women's age, education, the period of working as a fitness instructor or attending fitness classes and the frequency of teaching fitness classes or attending fitness classes, as well as avoiding poultry

Senlin Chen and Xiangli Gu: Effects of cardiorespiratory fitness and weight status on knowledge of physical activity and fitness, attitude toward physical education, and physical activity. The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of cardiorespiratory fitness and weight status on knowledge of physical activity and fitness (PAF knowledge), attitude toward physical education (PE), and physical activity. The findings reinforce the importance of promoting cardiorespiratory fitness in middle school PE as students acquire attitude, knowledge, and behaviors needed for active-living.

Amanda K. Buttery, Finbarr C. Martin. Knowledge, attitudes and intentions about participation in physical activity of older post-acute hospital inpatients. Most older people have suboptimal levels of habitual physical activity. This study investigated the knowledge, attitudes, intentions and barriers to participation in physical activity among older people recovering from acute illness or injury. These patients, potential benefactors from increased physical activity, had mixed knowledge and attitudes towards physical activity which was unrelated to frailty. These data provide insights relevant to the design and delivery of exercise-related health messages and interventions.

Yolanda Demetriou, Gorden Sudeck, Ansgar Thiel, Oliver Honer: The effects of school-based physical activity interventions on students' health-related fitness knowledge. A systematic review. This systematic review includes 34 studies examining the effects of school-based physical activity interventions on students' health-related fitness knowledge. The study design, methodological quality, and effectiveness of interventions on students' health-related fitness knowledge

were analyzed. These programmes can positively influence students' health-related fitness knowledge, but it remains unclear what the practical significance of these changes is. Further research is needed to clarify the influence of students' health-related fitness knowledge on reflection, understanding, physical activity behaviour, and overall physical literacy levels

3. Methodology

- 1) *Study Design*: Survey study
- 2) *Study Setting*: Dr. BR Ambedkar college of physiotherapy Bangalore 560045.
 - *Inclusion Criteria*: Physiotherapy students of Ambedkar college of physiotherapy
 - *Exclusion Criteria*:
 - Recent trauma or injury
 - Infection
 - Skin allergy
 - Recent surgery
- 3) *Sample Size*: 100 participants
- 4) *Sampling Method*: The questionnaire is framed from international physical activity to measure the type of physical activity in their daily life by students through google form.

4. Data Analysis

A. Demographic Data

The distribution is based on the age group of students between 18 years to 25 years who are studying in a D.R. Ambedkar College of Physiotherapy.

Fig. 1. Age group, 100 responses

Analysis: Among 100 students who participated 23% lies on an age group between 18-20, 49% lies on an age group of 20-23, 29% lies on an age group 23-25.

Analysis: From Fig. 2, among 100 individuals who participated there are 62% female and 38% male.

Analysis: From Fig. 3, out of 100 participants 18% is from 1st year 34% is from 2nd year 18% is from 3rd year and 30% is from final year.

Analysis: From Fig. 4, among 100 participants the pie chart is plotted according to the responds of the participants, there is 53% of students who does vigorous physical activity once in a

week, 20% students does it trice in a week, 20% students does it more than trice in a week and 3% student don't do the physical activity.

Fig. 2. Distribution based on gender

Fig. 3. Academic year

Fig. 4. During the last 7 days, on how many days did you do vigorous physical activities like heavy lifting, digging, aerobics, or fast bicycling?

Fig. 5. How much time did you usually spend doing vigorous physical activities on one of those days?

Analysis: Among 100 participants 52.50% students spend 15 mins for vigorous exercise 28.3% students spend 30 mins, 15.2% students spends 45 mins and 4% students spend 60 mins spends for vigorous exercise.

Fig. 6. During the last 7 days, on how many days did you do moderate physical activities like carrying light loads, bicycling at a regular pace, or double tennis? Do not include walking

Fig. 7. How much time did you usually spend doing moderate physical activities on one of those days?

Analysis: From Fig. 6, among 100 participants 42% students moderate physical activity once in a week, 21% students do thrice in a week, 36% students do more than thrice in a week whereas 1% don't do it.

Analysis: From Fig. 7, among 100 participants 52.5% spend 15 mins, 28.3% spends 30 mins, 15.2% spend 45 mins, whereas 9.10% spend 60 mins or more on a moderate exercise.

Fig. 8. During the last 7 days, on how many days did you walk for at least 10 minutes at a time?

Analysis: From Fig. 8, among 100 participants 34.04% students walk at least 10 mins once in a week, 20.20% students thrice in a week, 44.40 students more than thrice in a week.

Fig. 9. How much time did you usually spend walking on one of those days?

Analysis: From Fig. 9, among 100 participants 39.4% students walks 15 mins a day, 20.2% students walks 30 mins a day, 26.30% people walks 45 min a day, whereas 14.10% students walk more than 60 mins a day.

Fig. 10. During the last 7 days, how much time did you spend sitting useless on a week day?

Analysis: Among 100 participants 32.15% students' seat 15 mins useless in a day, 22.2% spends 30 mins, 19.2% 45 mins, whereas 26.3% spends 60 mins useless seating on a day.

5. Discussion

Regular physical activity is one of the most important things you can do for your health. Being physically active can improve your brain health, help manage weight, reduce the risk of disease, strengthen bones and muscles, and improve your ability to do everyday activities. Adults who sit less and do any amount of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity gain some health benefits. Only a few lifestyle choices have as large an impact on your health as physical activity. Everyone can experience the health benefits of physical activity – age, abilities, ethnicity, shape, or size do not matter.

This study was conducted to evaluate the knowledge and attitude of physiotherapy students toward fitness. The questionnaire is prepared from International physical activity questionnaire and distributed among the students to get their responses about their physical activity during their daily routine

Among the age distribution of the participants the minimum age is 18 whereas the maximum age is 25, according to the gender distribution 38% are male and 62% are female.

The level of knowledge demonstrated by the study finds the average level of knowledge among the physiotherapy students about fitness and the attitude towards the physical activity in their daily life.

6. Conclusion

This study has reinforced the need for a more focused approach to the education of physiotherapy students related to Fitness and physical activity related overall importance Education should also emphasize the vital role of physiotherapy in the society towards fitness.

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